

**Recruitment Practices and Precarious Working Circumstances of migrant women in
the Readymade Garments of Bangladesh.**

By
Tanjina Sultana

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fulfillment of the requirements for the Bachelor of Arts Honors degree.

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Supervisor:
Dr. Md. Selim Reza

Declaration of Originality

I, Tanjina Sultana, ID: 170091, hereby declare that:

- I have independently prepared and written the project report on the given topic as part of the requirements for my course at the Asian University for Women.
- This report has not been copied or used for any commercial purposes.
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- Furthermore, I have accurately acknowledged all primary sources of equipment and support in the development of this report.

.....
Tanjina Sultana

ID: 170091

Department of Politics, Philosophy & Economics (PPE)

Asian University for Women

11th Aug, 2022

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I extend my sincere gratitude goes to my peers and everyone who has been part of this journey. Their advice, support, and encouragement made this process both enriching and enjoyable.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in cursive script, appearing to read 'Tanjina Sultana', written in black ink.

Tanjina Sultana

ID: 170091

Department of Politics, Philosophy & Economics (PPE)
Asian University for Women

11th Aug, 2022

Abstract

This paper focuses on the recruitment process and the poor working conditions of the RMG sector of Bangladesh. To address the issues this paper discussed about the contribution of the female migrant workers to the growth of the RMG sector of Bangladesh. As the female migrant workers are covering a greater portion of the RMG sector, their contribution should be highlighted. After highlighting their contribution, the paper found the migrant female workers are leading a vulnerable life despite the larger contribution in the economy. Due to lack of addressing formal recruitment process, exploitation, verbal abuse and lack of compliance rules and regulations in the factories. The existing literature did not address the relationship between the recruitment process and the working conditions of the RMG sector in depth. The paper showed the relationship.

Keyword: Labor Rights, Worker Vulnerability, Exploitation, Compliance Standards, Economic Contribution, Factory Regulations, Occupational Hazards, Labor Migration, Employment Practices, Gender Disparity

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1. Introduction

The most promising economic sector in Bangladesh is the ready-made garments (RMG) industry, which is primarily an export-oriented region. Bangladesh generates significant foreign exchange revenue each year through the export of its manufactured garments to other nations.

This particular sector not only aids in Bangladesh's economic development but also helps the country's less educated and unemployed citizens. Since many members of these families work in the RMG business, many Bangladeshi households are dependent on it. Due to the fact that both male and female workers are employed in this field, Bangladesh's economy is benefiting from both genders' labor, just as it does when a man works. As the industry that significantly contributes to Bangladesh's economic development, and female workers are also contributing equally, we need to know the female migrant workers conditions during the recruitment procedure of this sector.

I want to specify the recruitment process, because the recruitment process is the starting chapter for a worker in this industry. The absence of compliances in the existing Bangladeshi factories, the bad working conditions, and the proper observation that was developed in 2006, which resulted in labor unrest and property damage, provide huge obstacles to the RMG industry despite its contribution to economic development (Ahmed & Ferdous, 2013). The statement demonstrates that despite the industry's significant contribution to economic growth, the sector's hiring procedures and working conditions receive little formal attention.

1.1 Justification of the Study

I am including the hiring process here because the recruitment process is also a part of ensuring the compliances. Since many factories are failing to fulfill the compliance requirements, they are failing to accommodate a formal recruitment process and as a result, the female migrant workers are taken advantage of during the hiring process. The hiring process should be conducted in a formal manner because it marks the beginning of a worker's involvement in the industry. Unexpectedly, due to the informal hiring process, these female employees who are helping to advance the economy and provide help for their families are not given the basic opportunities at work. For instance: Most of the time, appointment letters are not given to RMG sector employees. As a result, people labor in uncertain environments and are unsure of how long their jobs will last according to his wishes. The owner has the right to terminate her at any time. It represents exploitation. In order to highlight the significance of recruiting practices and working conditions for migrant women there, I feel the need to present background information on the contribution of the RMG industry to the economic prosperity of Bangladesh. In order to make people understand the recruitment process from the ground up, Since the RMG sector is helping to reduce Bangladesh's poverty problem, it is crucial to show the role the RMG business plays in the country's economy. Additionally, the various styles of Bangladeshi garment factories as well as the country's current RMG industry hiring procedures. It is high time to examine the hiring practices in the industry and comprehend the working circumstances in the RMG sector. Moreover, I want to examine migration in its broadest sense so that I can demonstrate how migrant female workers and Bangladesh's RMG sector are related. My paper basically consists of two parts. The first will demonstrate the hiring and recruitment process used in Bangladesh's RMG

sector, and the second will highlight the contribution made by female migrant workers in this industry.

1.2 History of contribution on economic growth of RMG sector in Bangladesh

The RMG sector did not evolve overnight in Bangladesh. It took several years to get established in the sector in Bangladesh. Bangladesh has made tremendous progress in continuously and consistently rising growth over the past three decades, with a gain of around one percentage point since the 1980s over the past five years, real GDP growth has averaged over 6%, which is significant. Better than the 4.7% global average for developing nations. Bangladesh recently crossed the USD 1,046 per capita income criterion to become a lower-middle income country at the start of FY2015–16. Bangladesh's per capita income in FY2017 was USD 1,514(Iqbal & Pabon, 2008). Also, other authors say, When Bangladesh gained its independence in 1971, the majority of observers of the young nation held a gloomy opinion of its chances for economic progress. Many believed that the nation would be stuck in a "below poverty level equilibrium trap" forever. Bangladesh has come a long way since then, despite the fact that there is little tolerance for complacency. Currently, exports, imports, factor markets, and commodity markets connect about two-fifths of the economy to the global economy; the economy is currently 40% open. Bangladesh may today claim to have evolved from largely being an aid-receiving nation to a trading nation. As mentioned above, the export-oriented RMG industry has played a crucial role in Bangladesh's economic restructuring (Bhattacharya et al., 2008). The role of our RMG entrepreneurs, domestic fiscal and financial, institutional policy support and incentives put in place by succeeding governments, significant RMG-supportive linkage activities within the domestic economy, and global market opportunities made it possible for us to tell a story that is, to be honest and true, unparalleled in the developing world. Jute and jute products gave the export and domestic economies an increase in economic activity through backward and forward links

(Bhattacharya et al., 2002). Also, the writers claim, the ready-made clothing (RMG) industry in Bangladesh, which is export-focused, began as a minor, unusual export industry in the late 1970s. In 1978, Ready Garments shipped from Bangladesh were only valued about \$69,000 when they sold their first consignment to the USA. Over the span of almost 20 years, exports climbed to US\$4.5 billion by FY2002. The sector has an average yearly growth rate of 15%, and has seen phenomenal growth in the last ten years. In fact, this was a developing sector with a startlingly rapid pace of expansion anywhere in the world. The industrial foundation that enabled such rapid expansion also saw a huge increase, growing from less than 50 firms in 1983 to more than 3,400 in 2002, as the number of RMG employees reached approximately 1.5 million (Bhattacharya et al., 2002). In addition, since Bangladesh's RMG industry began to flourish, it has boosted the country's economy each year. Recent research examines, The RMG industry has taken over as the nation's top export earner. By creating a sizable number of employment opportunities, particularly for the nation's poor, illiterate female workforce, this enterprise has boosted socioeconomic prospects. By manufacturing high-value commodities on a big scale, the industrial sector can increase social productivity by giving a large number of workers high-paying jobs. Additionally, developing nations can make significant foreign exchange by exporting manufactured goods, and this money can then be invested in newer models of equipment and technologies to enable quick advancement in technology. The significance of industrial growth as the economic backbone of Bangladesh. The importance of industrial development as a catalyst for Bangladesh's economic growth is further highlighted by the growing realization that the growth of the agricultural sector, one of the foundations of the nation's economy, critically depends on its backward and forward linkages with the industrial sector. As a result, the RMG sector has substantially aided in the empowerment of women by generating jobs. Bangladesh's RMG

sector, which employs uneducated female rural impoverished laborers, is recognized for its inexpensive labor (Mia & Akter, 2019).

1.3 Types of Readymade Garment factories in Bangladesh

There are two different types of RMG factories in Bangladesh. Among these, EPZs (Export Processing Zones) and Bengali factories are well-known and well-established. There are eight EPZs in use in Bangladesh. The Mongla export processing zone, the Chittagong export processing zone (CEPZ), the Dhaka export processing zone (DEPZ), the export processing zones of Comilla, Adamjee, Karnaphuli, and Ishwardi and the Uttara Export Processing Zone, Nilphamai, are among the export processing zones. The remaining factories in Bangladesh are known as Bengali factories. In addition, some factories are known as knit and woven factories as well based on their production. Such as: the factories which produce single yarn apparels are known as knit factories and the factories which produce double yarn or thread apparels are known as oven factories. Among the factories the EPZ's factories are contributing a lot to the economic growth of Bangladesh than the other factories. In the 1980s, Bangladesh jumped on the EPZ bandwagon. In Chittagong, the first export processing zone was established and opened for business in 1984. The zone currently covers 165 hectares of land and is home to 47 businesses with a combined investment of \$100 million and 16,682 employees (Dowla, 1997).

1.4 Types of existing recruitment practices in the RMG sector of Bangladesh

Typically, factories follow two kinds of recruitment. They are the traditional recruitment process and the E-recruitment process. During the hiring process, e-recruitment is used to recruit candidates, choose candidates, and connect with candidates and management

(Hoffman, 2001). Many authors have claimed that leveraging the power of the internet to identify the best fit applicants is achievable, including posting job advertisements electronically, scanning and storing resumes, conducting assessments, and contacting qualified individuals (Hogler, 1998). Additionally, it has been determined from the research of another scholar that e-recruitment has been developed in order to attract top prospects, maintain their company's profile and branding, and modernize the application and selection processes. Also, the following are some reliable conventional sources for finding employment candidates: Employee recommendations, newspaper ads, employment agencies, contingent businesses, job fairs, the internet, recruitment of underrepresented groups, walk-ins, and government employment services are just a few of the methods used to find employment (Bashar et al., 2015). Although there is a lot of recruitment taking place to work in the RMG sector, migrant female employees only obtain jobs there informally. Sometimes, the female employees learn about the openings via their friends, relatives, and neighbors who mostly work in the industry. When the plant management declares a vacancy for a designation, the employees are informed and spread the word. Sometimes, female migrant workers go door to door in the industries looking for work and manage to acquire positions there. As a consequence, the chances of getting exploitations get higher. They might face some unnecessary complications to get recruited to the factories. Examples include the demand for a percentage of the wage, verbal and physical abuse, discrimination, and the basis of unhygienic hiring practices, all of which actually contribute to poor working conditions. The reason I claim that the hiring process contributes to an unfavorable work environment for female migrant workers is that it sometimes lacks human rights terms and conditions. As a result, female employees are unaware of their rights and don't seem to be advocating for them because they believe the hiring process will continue and they should keep quiet. They consider the working conditions as their luck and they try to adapt with the continuation of

the process. The sorrows and pains of the female migrant workers in Bangladesh's RMG sector go unspoken, and they are described in the literature as being vulnerable.

1.5 Migration

Moving from one place to another is referred to as "migration." It also refers to moving individuals from one location to another. It has been identified as a driver of social transformation. Social construction is changed through migration. It makes a significant contribution to the economic growth of a nation. Every nation where migrants bring their labor benefits from having them there. Give them the respect and decency they deserve for who they are as people and as employees (Somavia). To take advantage of better economic prospects, people relocate from one location to another. Other factors can also contribute to migration. In the majority of countries around the world, push and pull factors are considered to be the main reasons for migration. Migration has many negative aspects as well as positive aspects for growth. In the literature, migration takes many various forms. In terms of migration, internal migration, external migration, immigration, and emigration are all important factors. I chose to focus on internal migration in this study because it occurs when people move from one province to another inside a state. It is an example of rural-to-urban migration. I am bringing up rural urban migration because it includes both male and female migrants who relocate from rural areas to urban areas in quest of employment. They are typically unskilled, less educated workers. They attempt to find employment in Bangladesh's RMG sector despite their inadequate education and lack of work abilities, they subsequently land jobs in the RMG sector and support Bangladesh's economic development. Due to the fact that there are few alternatives or better employment prospects for poor, unskilled women, these women play a significant role in supporting the RMG business. Because women are

more submissive, pliable, and less expensive than men, employers prefer to hire them.

Women workers are more controllable. They do not object when given flexible working conditions, and they are also considered as less prone to organization and to external "anti-management propaganda" (Khan 2001, as cited in Sikdar et al., 2014). In addition, according to estimates, the morbidity rate is 52 percent for slum residents and 42 percent for female garment manufacturing workers (Afsar, 1999). The numbers highlight how vulnerable female garment workers are. It is regrettable that the majority of the country, which contributes to economic prosperity, lacks clean housing for a healthy lifestyle. However, the most important aspect of every nation's internal movement is rural-urban migration, This effectively illustrates the gap in the economy, opportunities, and standard of living between regions (Islam, 2006, as cited in Ishtiaque et al., 2013). Development of towns is inextricably linked to migration, particularly rural-urban movement, as laborers from rural regions fill the vast majority of urban centers' labor needs (Harris 1970, as cited in Ishtiaque et al., 2013). Even though the rural-urban migrants experience wretched lives, their migration helps to stimulate economic progress. They are being deprived of every aspect of opportunities in their life. They are coming to the cities in search of better lifestyles due to lack of success in the agricultural sphere nowadays. A recent study showed, The most important characteristic driven by the economic benefits is that many rural households leave their homes to work as a result of the paucity of agricultural laborers and the aging of agricultural production in rural areas. Migration is characterized as either a temporary or permanent departure from the rural areas to metropolitan centers, often within the nation's borders (Al Maruf et al., 2022). According to history, urbanization leads to migration. The country's urban population increased by 44.63 percent from 1951 and 1961. Mostly as a result of Muslim immigration, which began in British India in 1947. In response to poor rural conditions, the majority of immigrants settled in urban areas, which further accelerated its expansion. This was made

possible by the creation of new centers for production and administration (Khan & Mamun, 1982). Rural-Migration is the process which results in excessive pressure for the urban areas. Such as it increases pressure on the job sectors. An estimation says, similar to LDCs, Bangladesh has had phenomenal urban population growth in recent years that hasn't eased. This expansion has been mostly attributed to people moving from rural to urban regions, which has led to concerns. Urban occupations are under a lot of strain as a result. However, it is often more difficult and expensive to create jobs in the urban sector than in the rural sector due to the fact that the bulk of jobs in the urban industrial sector require considerable complementary resource inputs (Bhuyan et al., 2001). In addition rural urban migration contributes a lot to consumption. In general, remittances to rural regions increase consumption. They also support the growth of the building and agriculture industries. Remittances also aided in the creation of savings, which served as the main source of capital in the lack of readily available institutional credit. The market for land tenancy in rural areas has been boosted by migration and remittances. The prevalent idea that migration transmits rural poverty to urban regions has been refuted by research. There is a wealth of data showing that metropolitan immigrant households' incomes have increased after moving there. At the same time, remittances from migrating family members have increased household incomes in rural sending areas (Afsar & Rita, 2013).

1.6 Problem of the Statement

The purpose of this study is to identify the inadequate hiring practices and working conditions for Bangladeshi RMG sector's female migrant workers. After addressing the concerns, I will present my problem statement to help draw connections. Sorting through the existing literature that addresses the issues faced by female migrant workers in Bangladesh's RMG sector is necessary to identify the problems. I will discuss the conditions of female

migrant workers (the rural urban migrants) in Bangladesh in order to draw attention to the challenges faced by those employed as migrant workers in Bangladesh's RMG sector. I chose this issue since it will keep the rest of my analysis coherent as I examine these conditions. The interactions between the rural and urban poor are likely to be impacted by structural factors such as shifts in the social, political, and economic environment at the international, national, and local levels (Afsar, 1999). People move from rural to urban regions for this reason. Children and women are often included among the migrants. I will add some material that specifically addresses the issues of female migrant workers since my study solely considers female migrant workers. Observers are concerned about migrant flows to major cities in Bangladesh as well. The 1974 famine saw a sharp surge in rural-urban migration flows (BBS, 1996, as cited in Ullah, 2004). As a result, the proportion of rural migrants in the urban population increased from 5.2 percent in 1961 to 8.9 percent. Rural-urban migration shows a clear selectivity with regard to age, sex, caste, marital status, education, and occupation (Millington, 2000, as cited in Ullah, 2004). In several cases, men would give their wives death incentives (Simon, 1997, as cited in Ullah, 2004). Individual migration also has a demographic influence in addition to social, cultural, and socioeconomic effects. Low fertility in migrant households is caused by the physical separation of husbands and wives brought on by migration, which limits the female partner's ability to conceive (Hossain, 2001, as cited in Ullah, 2004). Another study shows 3.20 million women, or 85% of the 4 million workers in the RMG industry, are employed, with the majority being economically disadvantaged women [5]. By offering the most employment chances, Bangladesh's RMG sector has, to a commendable extent, reduced the burden of its excessive unemployment rate. This industry has improved the underserved segment of the population, fundamentally altering the socioeconomic landscape of the nation. This is a blatant example of how important the industry is to the wider economy. Examine the elements of the work environment that

contribute to lower productivity. The quantity of managerial tasks is what matters. Offering of appropriate fringe benefits, management, working practices, and organization, in the workplaces that seem to have been the main obstacle to increased productivity. Additionally, it has been noted that supervision, subordinates, coworkers' inefficiency as one of the key factors that influence work output [9]. The promotion of Employees and the working environment's flexibility three essential productivity factors: Too much labor, inadequate rewards, and little opportunities for advancement are all factors that contribute to poor supervision and employee involvement [10]. The two biggest barriers to productivity are ineffective work and organizational structure design by management and inadequate management leadership in demonstrating and guiding change [11]. According to a survey, nine out of ten workers said that the quality of the workplace influences employees' attitudes and boosts productivity [12]. Another research study has demonstrated that hazardous and risky working conditions, such as inadequate ventilation, poor lighting, excessive noise, etc., have an impact on employees' productivity and health [13](Saha & Mazumder, 2015). The entire scenario demonstrates the need of setting up a healthy work environment for factory workers, where the migrant female workers are also included. These studies demonstrate how Bangladesh's RMG sector's subpar working conditions have an impact on both production and the country's migrant female employees. The issue with working conditions has received the most attention in the literature. Surprisingly, the hiring process, which is thought of as the beginning of the trip, was not extensively highlighted. It is time to properly research the subject.

1.7 Goals of the Study

The study's main objectives are listed in the list below: Examining the working conditions in Bangladesh's RMG sector is the goal of this study. To observe the hiring practices of the RMG industry in Bangladesh. The study also tries to draw a connection

between Bangladesh's RMG industry and female migration. The reasons for and contributing aspects in Bangladesh's RMG industry recruitment procedure. To carefully consider whether or not the workplace tolerates prejudice. To determine whether or not a migrant woman worker can thrive at her job. Since research looks into the facts and draws fresh conclusions about a certain topic, this study also aims to determine whether or not migrant female workers are given enough possibilities at work and whether they are subjected to any verbal, physical, or mental abuse throughout the hiring process. Whether or not the female migrant workers are receiving their just compensation. In general, this study aims to investigate whether or not the sector's hiring practices and working conditions are hospitable to migrant female workers. The study also tries to determine whether or not opportunities differ from factory to factory. The study will demonstrate the various perspectives on hiring procedures and working conditions amongst younger and more experienced migrant female workers in Bangladesh's RMG industry.

1.8 Research Questions

The study's questions are crucial to look into since they attempt to address issues with hiring procedures and working conditions in Bangladesh's readymade garment industry. We must determine whether or not female migrant workers are well-facilitated because we are all aware of their impact on the economic development of the industry in Bangladesh. We must recognize their economic standing because of their contribution to the advancement of our country. It is crucial to start with the hiring process in order to determine whether or not they have good facilities in their factories. It is important to emphasize the research questions in order to learn more about the current situation of the industry's hiring procedures. Otherwise, without posing the questions, we are unable to identify the real state of Bangladesh's RMG industry's subpar hiring methods and working conditions. Additionally, the recruitment questions should be highlighted since they address some issues with the processes by asking questions. The surveys are organized into three areas that represent the recruiting process, the many types of recruitment processes now in use in Bangladesh's sector, and the subpar working conditions in Bangladesh's RMG industry. Participants are urged to answer the questions truthfully in order to draw attention to the issues with the current procedures.

2. Literature Review

FA (Multi Fiber Agreement) quota-free status, flexible import policies for accessories, and a drop in loan rates have all contributed to the rise in these businesses. The garment sector's share of global export revenue increased from 3.89 percent in 1983–1984 to 76 percent in 2006–2007. (Golam Faruk, 2009, as cited in Wahid et al., 2020). As a result, the sector grows to be a massive industry that provides the lion's share of the nation's foreign exchange and has given rise to a number of capable private entrepreneurs who can aid in the expansion and advancement of a country. The number of manufactured factories in the nation has increased to over 5000, and there are currently 3.6 million people working in the RMG sector (BGMEA, Members' Directory 2010-2011, as cited in Sikdar et al., 2014). The availability of female labor is one of the primary factors contributing to the growth of this sector. As a result, Bangladesh's RMG sector offers underprivileged rural women in the nation the opportunity to work in factories and change their socioeconomic status and way of life (Mahmud, 2003, as cited in Kabeer & Mahmud, 2004). As a result, women make up 80% of the workforce in this industry (Golam Faruk, 2009, as cited in Islam et al., 2016), with the majority of them being migrant workers from rural and suburban areas. Another scholar argues, in countries that are developing economically, there is a large-scale rural-urban migration as well as a shift in employment from agriculture to industry and services (Lewis, 1954; Harris and Todaro, 1970, as cited in Amirapu et al., 2022). Despite contributing to economic growth, the female workers' miserable lives are unexposed due to lack of investigation. A study shows, because there has been relatively little research specifically on the patterns of livelihood of women workers, very little is known about the socioeconomic situations of textile workers. The economic, social, and health situations of garment workers have been the subject of numerous studies conducted at various times by various scholars throughout the world. The majority of female factory workers gave their access to

employment a good rating because it was an improvement over their pre-job lives, according to Kabeer's study from 2000. Paul-Majumder (2003) conducted research on the physical and mental health of textile workers and how these conditions impact labor productivity, the competitiveness of the clothing sector on the worldwide market, and the working conditions of employees, particularly female employees. Many employees were observed to continue working despite having a variety of illnesses and ailments (Ali et al., 2008). The majority of the health issues that garment workers experienced were caused by workplace risks, such as extended working hours, a lack of leave options, crowded and overcrowded workspaces, etc. According to Halim and Kabir (2005, as cited in Uddin & Salah, 2008), women working in the RMG sector were given particular attention while examining the positive and negative effects of globalization on women within the context of the current unequal gender division of labor. In the RMG sector, which generates the majority of the nation's foreign exchange, women make up the lion's share of the total labor force. However, due to a lack of technical training and expertise, women were readily exploited (Ali, et al. 2008). Another scholarly article also supports that women are neglected and demonstrates that, as a result, men are assigned responsibility for all affairs outside the home while women are limited to domestic duties (N. Kibria, 1995, as cited in Kibria & Nazil, 1998). Purdah is a strong source of exclusion because it isolates women and creates the socially acceptable conduct for them to remain ignorant, dependent on, and inferior to men. Because they are not expected to use their education in their adult lives, girls' education is accordingly given less priority than that of boys. Because a girl will eventually be married and live in her husband's home, poor people think it is a waste of money to invest in her education. Furthermore, due to early pregnancies and rising dowry demands, girls marry in their adolescent years (S. F. Rashid, 2006, as cited in Khosla & Nidhi, 2009). Parents fear rape or other crimes like sexual harassment may happen to older single girls (S. F. Rashid, 2006, as cited in Khosla & Nidhi,

2009). In contrary, another author denied the thought and argues, the causes for the high proportion of women working in the global apparel industry have been covered in great detail in the literature, thus they will not be examined here (Nash and Fernandez-Kelly, 1983; Elson and Pearson, 1981; Beneria, 2003, as cited in Kabeer & Mahmud, 2004). An author claimed that in order to understand Bangladesh's internal migration system, geographic push-pull dynamics that balance the enticing and discouraging aspects of migration and economic models that are driven by financial disparities across locations are frequently cited as the causes of rural to urban migration (Marshall and Rahman 2013, as cited in Biswas et al., 2019). According to Giani (2006, as cited in Biswas et al., 2019), economic opportunities are one of the main factors influencing migration from rural to urban areas in the country, along with "bright city lights." (Deshingkar and Grimm 2005, as cited in Biswas et al., 2009). Hossain (2005, as cited in Biswas et al., 2019) Utilizing a data set of 500 people of Dhaka City, it was determined that natural disasters (such as river erosion) and accompanying family members were likely causes of relocation. These studies, however, only included a small number of places (mostly Dhaka) and had small sample sizes. An analysis of district-wide data from two censuses (1991 and 2011, as cited in Biswas et al., 2019) revealed three distinct causes of migration: the state of the economy, the quality of public services, and environmental concerns. But they failed to consider the role that household factors had in these causes (Marshall and Rahman, 2013, as cited in Biswas et al., 2019). This research compiled the main reasons for urban migration and any potential contributions from pertinent sociodemographic characteristics using data from a national household survey (Biswas et al., 2009). Which is applicable for the female migrants as well. However, the rate of the participation of female migrants in the RMG sector of Bangladesh was specified. The study states, numerous studies have revealed that Bangladesh's garment industry has been dominated by migrant labor. According to the BIDS 1990 survey results, 83% of male

workers and 69% of female workers were from rural regions (Zohir and Paul-Majumder 1996, as cited in Zohir & Chaudhuri, 2001). Another statistic shows, the garment factory employs both married and single people. 55 percent of married and 45 percent of single female employees were polled. It is noteworthy that about half of the female workers in the RMG industry are unmarried women who are also providing for their families. They are occasionally harassed by their male equivalent. Now more married women are entering the workforce, particularly in the RMG industry. They argued that the industry owner's perception that married women are less devoted to the job market has to be altered (Sikder et al., 2014). In addition, about one-third of the women who were interviewed were employed in households with incomes that were below the poverty line. More than 80% of women value abroad career opportunities as a result of their experience working in Dhaka's ready-to-wear sector. Nine out of ten women had moved away in order to increase their income and access better job opportunities. They sent remittances that accounted for roughly 46 percent of their household's earnings. Increasing numbers of research evaluates how women's access to microcredit, education, and involvement in the labor force all contribute to female empowerment. The relationship between migration and empowerment is significantly less stressed in Bangladesh. Furthermore, it is frequently claimed that existing research on empowerment does not explicitly state the contribution of men to women's empowerment (Kabeer, 1999, as cited in Saha et al., 2015). Rarely are issues of empowerment juxtaposed with those of vulnerability. As most migrating women assess potential issues against potential advantages of moving, I would contend that empowerment and vulnerability must be taken into account. There are not many advantages in real-world situations that can be accomplished without suffering. As a result, I view Women's migration to the manufacturing industry from other countries is seen as a process of empowerment that increases their ability to "discover new options...a repertory of choices," but it also increases their susceptibility to

institutional exploitation and gender discrimination (Balitwala, 1994, as cited in Afsar & Rita, 2004). That is the position of female migrant workers in the literature. To ensure a healthy environment for the workplace of the RMG sector, we need to ensure the HRM practices in the sector. To demonstrate the current conditions of HRM in the sector, an author states, below is a description of the actual human resource management (HRM) situation at BHT Garments Ltd. in the apparel industry. Human Resource Management (HRM) was not clearly presented at the outset of this industry, but it currently plays a significant role. They currently attempt to implement HRM techniques, however they do not do it correctly. The hiring and choosing procedure are not very conventional. Rules and regulations are not always followed by everyone. At mid- and lower-level positions, compensation packages are little; nevertheless, at the top level, they are standard. Although it is vital to improve performance and productivity, the personnel do not have access to training facilities. The work to boost productivity is typically the emphasis of the company. This aids in achieving the organizational objective. They consistently attempt to compare non-standard quality with quantity. Less concerned with advancing their careers dearth of reliable management information department data that is sufficient, accurate, and current (MIS) although it should be based on performance and is occasionally not given appropriately, salary and promotion decisions are made based on seniority. In some cases, nepotism also plays a role. A lack of job descriptions and job analysis procedures for the staff, which can often make it difficult for lower-level employees to pinpoint their precise responsibilities. The majority of employees experience job stress, which does not necessarily promote productivity. All departments do not have enough current equipment, such as computers and other technologies. The company typically does not run advertisements in media outlets including the internet & daily newspapers. The majority of workers don't feel secure in their jobs. Although there are few employees in this workplace, it is a good working environment (Chowdhury & Hassan,

2015). Another author strongly agreed with the necessity of establishing the social compliances in the factories of the RMG sector. The author said, the primary foreign currency-earning sector in the industry producing ready-made clothing (RMG) has the highest employment rate in Bangladesh. Bangladesh sold garments worth \$10.7 billion USD in 2008, or about 3.87 percent of the \$276 billion USD in global garment exports as a whole (EPB, 2008; BB, 2008, as cited in Ahmed & Ferdous, 2013). An author includes, numerous studies indicate that companies prioritize HR planning. They consequently place less emphasis on HR practice. By connecting a bridge, HR supervises personnel at all levels of the organization. Manpower planning and forecasting methods are used by HR experts. HR managers look for jobs that are completed exactly by staff members. As a result, HR managers should select the best candidates for the job while also paying attention to how satisfied current employees are. The RMG sector's situation with regard to HR practices, working conditions, and job satisfaction was examined in some earlier studies. For instance, Paul Majumder & Begum (2000, as cited in Khosla & Nidhi, 2009) described the RMG industry's conditions at the time of their early research (1990; 1993 and 1997, as cited in Khosla & Nidhi, 2009). They discovered that both male and female garment industry workers put in roughly 12 hours per day, that leave opportunities and weekly holidays were scarce, that career advancement was halted, that factories were overcrowded, congested, and inadequately ventilated, that air pollution was rife, that there were inadequate fire safety precautions, that there was no lunchroom, and that there were few access points to clean drinking water (Akter et al., 2016). Also, the job dissatisfaction is being highlighted in terms of women workers. A study shows, In the RMG industry, the number of working women is rising steadily. The majority of them are mothers, and they have crucial roles to perform both at home and at work. Their displeasure at work typically spreads to their coworkers, and word-of-mouth may be quite damaging to a business. The corporation can use the complaints

from disgruntled employees as a source of data to create business plans and make tactical decisions. The Ready-Made Garments sector's rapid growth and development have also led to numerous internal management issues: a lack of employee work satisfaction has made it difficult to raise product quality. Job insecurity, low pay, poor working conditions, and high levels of stress are factors influencing mother employees' happiness in the present Ready Made Garments sectors. These issues have troubled mother employees for years.

Bangladesh's primary industry for generating foreign currency is ready-made clothing.

Working mothers make up three-quarters of RMG Industries' workforce. In this way, a happy employee can deliver high-quality goods to overseas customers, who will then be more devoted to the business. The most crucial factors influencing organizational effectiveness in the RMG sector are overseas customers. The RMG business has different working conditions and stress levels than other industries. Consequently, a variety of factors influence mother employees' job happiness in the sector (Akter et al., 2017). In addition, HR strategies are significantly correlated with employee turnover and hierarchical responsibility. Billahet and others (2009) Rab (1991, as cited in Khan & Md, 2017), investigated the HRM procedures in 24 start-up businesses operating in Dhaka. He points out that for recruiting, responder interaction was the most important method (58%) and trailed behind advertisements in daily newspapers walk-in interviews (21%). (13 percent) and structure Message boards (8 percent). All of the companies, with the exception of one, employed interviews and work sample testing to select their personnel. Another study will focus on Khulna Hardboard Mills Ltd general workforce management (HRM) procedures. The regulations governing hiring, the selection process, the management of compensation, the Concerns about safety and health as well as the connection between management and labor were all looked at. The investigation turned up a number of problems with staff administration practices, such as faculty conflict, erratic supervision, inaccurate evaluation, a high proportion of adversarial neighborhood

employees, absences, insufficient preparation programs, a dearth of aptitude tests, favoritism and preference in worker advancement and choice, poor contemporary relationships, insufficient pay, and poor welfare and welfare. (Taher, 1992, as cited in Khan & Md, 2017). Song and Medcof (2013, as cited in Khan & Md, 2017), Entrepreneurial HR arrangements (exploratory) are found to be less classified than supporting HR systems in terms of personnel selection, performance evaluation, and the relationship between training and performance-compensation (exploitative). The conclusion states that HR practices and implications should vary depending on how delicately organizational processes are handled. (Shelly 1994, as cited in Khan & Md. 2017) examined the HR functions in light of Bangladesh's modernization process. He observed that one of the real issues Bangladesh's industrial zones were facing was inadequate Practices in human resource management (HRM). Most HR implications, including HR positioning, organization, determination, progression, execution assessment, remuneration, motives, and modern relationships, were not reasonably implemented in commercial businesses (Khan & Md 2017). However, the literature agreed on the contribution of rural female migrant workers in Bangladesh's RMG industry. Some authors said the female workers are being neglected in the literature and some of the authors said, there is huge literature for the women workers, which actually contradicts each other. Some of the authors showed some statistics to show the contribution of female migrant workers in the RMG sector of Bangladesh. Some authors argued that due to lack of skill the female migrant workers are exploited whereas my research shows, the female workers are gaining skills still they are discriminated against. In addition, some authors have shown the necessity of the adoption of HR procedures in Bangladesh's RMG industry, some of them examined the practices. Also, the poor working conditions and the job dissatisfactions are also being highlighted. Surprisingly, no one focuses on the recruitment process of the RMG sector. That is the existing gap in the literature.

3. Research Methodology

To conduct this research, I will consider both primary and secondary sources. The research will follow the mixed approach, which contains the qualitative and the quantitative approach both. I will follow the mixed approach because some parts of the research will consider the scholarly articles, some secondary data. In order to show the RMG sector's contribution to economic growth, I will apply some statistics and census on my paper to demonstrate the economic contribution of the RMG sector in Bangladesh. I wish to submit the primary data here because I need to apply some statistics, which might be very specific. If I consider the part in the secondary data, the integrity of the data could be lost. Also, the readers can verify the statistics. However, as I have stated before I will show the recruitment process I will also add the working conditions for female migrant workers in the RMG sector. In order to show the internal procedure, I have developed some research questions which I mentioned in the introductory part of my paper. Since I need to seek assistance from the participants to conduct my research, this part will follow the qualitative approach. I am considering a qualitative approach here because the purpose of the research is to raise social awareness. In order to raise social awareness, I need to arrange such an environment where the workers can speak and demonstrate some issues in the sector. Since, the part is related to their opinion and thoughts, the part will follow the qualitative approach's integral part. I sought assistance from the participants who are engaged in various RMG sectors in Bangladesh to answer the questions. Dhaka and Chittagong were the main sources of participants, in my opinion. Twenty people were recruited to help me with my study. Different types of participation were created. Some of the participants came from Chittagong EPZ and Dhaka. Some of them are from factories in Bengal. I divided them up into several groups to illustrate the distinction between migrant female employees in EPZ and Bengali factories. Since the female migrant workers are employed in the same factories as the

German manufacturers, I want to draw attention to the inequality that exists between the EPZ factories and the Bengali factories. It is regrettable that female migrant employees are given more possibilities than female migrant workers in Bengali factories. Furthermore, I will ask a few former female employees who took part in my research since I wanted to see if the behaviors had changed or not. Participants' ages will be restricted to those who are at least 35. From the age of 18, the calculation will begin. The range of ages from 18 to 35 was taken into consideration since I also wanted to examine how older people and young female migrant workers rated the hiring procedures and working conditions. I have made an effort to include diversity in my work because different people have varied views on the procedures and hiring practices used in the RMG sector. This has allowed the criteria to be properly justified. To ensure that the participants could address the major topic of the study, the questions were divided into various sections. To ask the questions, each participant has to spend twenty to twenty-five minutes. The questions were open ended questions so that the participants could add their opinions according to their will. The research will be conducted through an in-depth interview so that the participants can provide the internal information. Since it was not possible for me to physically attend, the interviews will take place online. The following ethical guidelines were followed in order for me to perform this research. The questions were created to examine the specifics of the application procedure and the working conditions for female migrant workers in Bangladesh's readymade garment industry. The inquiries were extensive and open-ended. There were alternatives for including participant opinions. Twenty women who were migrants participated in the study. I called them and requested the interview over the phone. During the call, the automatic recording system was running, and the interviewees were very cordial. The data collection process lasted seven days. The information was translated from Bengali to English after I gathered it in July. Because the participants spoke the local Bengali language, translation was simpler. I think

their interviews were translated in a proper manner because I am from Bangladesh and I contain the Bengali language within myself, whatever the participants said that was easier for me to understand and translate them into English.

3.1. Ethical considerations

Basic details such as name, age, and contact info will be concealed. I am the only one who has access to the essential data. The interviewees were not coerced into participating. Before setting up the interview, I got the participants' permission. The interviews were held at night to give the participants plenty of time to express their ideas and worries. Each and every word was meticulously recorded since their ideas and notions are important. To make the research questions easier for the participants to grasp, they were translated into Bengali. The participants were not required to answer every question, but they were encouraged to do so as much as they could so that I could create a relaxed environment with them. I explained the need for the study to the participants before asking them any questions so that they could open up about the delicate topics related to the hiring process and the working conditions in the RMG industry. I reassure the participants that their information won't be shared with the workers or the owners of the factories, encouraging them to speak honestly. I was accessible to the attendees so that they may ask questions if they had any questions. Since it is an open-ended interview, the participants were asked to explain the detailed information so that any falsified information could be detected. The interview procedures ensure the genuine information. I have asked the participants questions twice and sometimes thrice to ignore the falsified data. It was too difficult to detect the falsified data though I could manage to detect them by confusing the participants and encouraging them to reveal the truth. During the interview, the participants were asked to keep distance from their family members so that the family members could not manipulate them. I asked the participants to arrange a calm

atmosphere so that they could not get distracted easily. Moreover, in order to get the authentic data for the quantitative part, I got access to some authentic search engines so that the data can be verified easily.

4. Findings

The hiring process from the ground up, it is important to emphasize the significance that the RMG sector plays in the Bangladeshi economy. This is because the RMG sector helps to alleviate poverty in Bangladesh. In addition, the diverse employment practices used by Bangladesh's RMG industry and the country's various garment factories. It is imperative that we investigate hiring methods in the sector and have an understanding of working conditions there. In order to show the connection between migrant female workers and Bangladesh's RMG sector, I also want to look at migration in its broadest sense. My article is mainly split into two parts. The first will demonstrate the hiring and recruiting practices used by the RMG sector in Bangladesh, and the second will highlight the contribution that female migrant workers contribute to this industry. The findings of the study are provided below:

Bangladesh sold RMG goods worth US\$4.5 billion in FY2002. She contributed 3.2 percent of all clothing imports into the US, 3.3 percent to the EU, and 3.0 percent to Canada. These nations recognize Bangladesh as a tiny nation with a sizable presence. RMG promotes Bangladesh as a tourist and investment destination by acting as the nation's flagship product everywhere. These effects are hard to measure, but without them it's possible the nation would not have the ability to predict a trajectory of quick growth and growing levels of life. As a result, it is important to acknowledge RMG's direct and indirect contributions to Bangladesh (Bhattacharya et al., 2002). Another author argues, The RMG sector works to develop human resources in addition to supporting the national economy. It makes a substantial contribution to gender equality, socioeconomic growth of women, and the gross domestic product (GDP). Over the past three decades, RMG has established a solid global reputation for apparel sourcing. In terms of nominal GDP, Bangladesh ranks 37th (as of 2014 estimates) and 36th (as of 2012-2013 estimates), with \$419.2 billion. 6.12% GDP Growth is anticipated in the year of 2013–14. The RMG industry makes for more than thirteen percent

of the GDP Bangladesh. By providing jobs to both sexes in order to increase GDP and generate 80% of all export revenue in foreign currency, the RMG sector aids in the reduction of poverty in Bangladesh (Rahman et al., 2015). In order to show the contribution of the RMG sector to Bangladesh's GDP, a statistical analysis has given below:

Table 1: *RMG and Its Contribution in Total Export*

Year	RMG export (in million us\$)
1983-84	31.57
1989-90	624.16
1995-96	2547.13
2001-02	4583.75
2007-08	10699.80
2012-13	21515.73
2013-14	24491.88

Note: Source: BGMEA 2015a, as cited in Islam et al., 2016

Also, the author argues, the RMG industry of Bangladesh empowers female migrant workers. The author has showed a statistic, which is given below:

Table 2: *Empowerment of Female Migrant Workers in the RMG Industry of Bangladesh*

Country	No of Workers	% Of Female
Bangladesh	4 Million	90
Sri Lanka	31, 200	81
India	5.3 Million	38
Nepal	5,200	18
Pakistan	9, 12,000	15

Note: Source: BGMEA 2015a, as cited in Islam et al., 2016

Both of the statistics show the contribution of economic growth and women empowerment in Bangladesh. To show the Contribution of Migrant Workers in Bangladesh more, I will add some data. An author argues, during the 1970s and 1980s, export-oriented industrialization became a prominent role in the development plans of various Asian countries (Lee, 1984, as cited in Uddin & School of Business, 2008). It has been discovered that there are certain universal patterns in the gender-related labor utilization patterns and export manufacturers' makeup (UN, 1995, as cited in Uddin & Salah, 2008). The apparel industry is the one factor that contributes the most to foreign exchange earnings. Since the industries require a lot of manpower, the availability of inexpensive labor, particularly female labor, has enticed both domestic and foreign businesspeople to develop RMG stands for ready-made garment industry. Though some gender-specific aspects of labor exploitation have also been identified, they promoted the hiring of numerous female workers in the RMG sector. It has been highlighted that the RMG sector of Bangladesh promoted the employment of female workers. But the continuation of debate going on the empowerment of women. According to World Bank data, the analyses and research it has generated provide crucial

insights into the processes of economic and social empowerment for underprivileged women in low-income developing countries. It has been hotly debated whether and to what extent RMG or garment employment has improved the lives of women workers. The limitations of a concentration on individualized economic empowerment, however, have been a source of dissatisfaction for attentive watchers of gendered social development in Bangladesh, as this study shows. Although certain women may be able to negotiate the "structures of restraint" that influence their lives and relationships through paid labor, what about the systems of restriction themselves? What does the recognition of women's rights and responsibilities in the care economy, as well as their roles as citizens and political participants in society, signify as a result of their widespread, prominent employment in the vital RMG sector? Has it helped place a greater emphasis on women's and girls' education and skills? Has it resulted in improvements to women's rights to public space and safety? Has the way that women are perceived as citizens changed so that they are now recognized as distinct individuals who can act as economic agents rather than just as mothers in the background? How has labor politics influenced women's political emancipation? (Hossain & Naomi, 2012). There is ongoing debate over whether the RMG industry supports the empowerment of women. Female migrant workers make up a larger part of the workforce overall. It is required to display some data in order to illustrate the situation of female migrant workers in Bangladesh's RMG sector, and the following data is offered: Growing numbers of rural Bangladeshi women have looked for wage work since the 1970s, particularly in the fields of agricultural labor and excavation, brick-breaking, building, and road upkeep. Specifically, two categories of women have been more prone to take on these tasks: women living in low-income homes headed by men, and household heads who are women. Consequently, poverty and the lack of a masculine. The women who are wage-seekers typically have one or both of these roles. In many respects, placing focus on these "push" elements is consistent with the idea of the

importance of cultural barriers in preventing women's wage advancement employment. That is, women only defy cultural prohibitions against participating in paid jobs when they are under the intense strain of extreme poverty. Especially in employment that demands females to be in public places with a majority of men (Kibria & Nazil, 1998). To illustrate the position of a female migrant worker of RMG sector of Bangladesh an estimation is given below: Between 1983 and 2000, Bangladesh's female labor force participation rate increased significantly. During this time, the RMG sector developed swiftly, attracting many disadvantaged, illiterate women from Bangladesh's rural districts have moved to the city to work in this field. According to several studies, women were chosen for the RMG industry because they were "docile," could work extra, and could be paid less. 6, 11, 12 Males predominate in the sector's higher-paying, powerful jobs with sway over labor regulation. Significant gender inequality occurs because these ideas and traditional gender norms are still prevalent. The effects on female workers, however, have not been thoroughly studied (Akhter et al., 2017). That is how the rural migrant female workers are being ignored and their roles are also not acknowledged. As a result, they are considered as vulnerable in society. The data was gathered through many studies. The results of my investigation also point to similar conditions for migrant female employees in Bangladesh's ready-to-wear industries. The other eighteen attendees, with the exception of two of my participants, concurred that the recruitment process does not follow the established procedures. The Readymade Garment businesses' working conditions are seen as less sexually exploitative by the teenage participants in my research. It is urged that they speak out against any form of sexual exploitation. On the other hand, the elder participants in my study claimed that before the compliances in the factories of the sector in Bangladesh, exploitation was developed in various ways. One quotation from the interview is, "I have seen many of the women being sexually harassed or exploited and I did not see anyone to raise their voice". Whereas,

nowadays, the situation has changed. Still the teenage female workers are not satisfied. One participant said, it is quite unhygienic to make a balance between the house time and the working hours. Also, I need to come back to my house and prepare food for my family and I cannot enjoy a sound sleep due to the responsibility of the family and the factory". Also, she said the production pressure is excessive and she says, "The line chief, supervisor convert into a demon, if I fail to achieve the target in one hour. They use slang to criticize me and send me to the HR and the HR authorities are also on behalf of the production. They convinced me to produce more and contribute to the growth of the factory". That is how the procedure is going on and she said, the compliance is to show the formal environment of the factory. No one cares for the welfare of the migrant female workers, rather everyone is busy with the production".

I have broken each component into a few smaller sections to better illustrate the study's findings, which are listed below:

4.1 Recruitment Process according to the Participants.

The participants were questioned regarding the current hiring practices in Bangladesh's RMG industry. The participants' responses are placed in quotation marks below in order to address the questions. Participant1: "I took the job by myself. I went to the factory gate and I talked to the security guards and asked if there was a vacancy or not in the factory. The guard said there is a vacancy, and was taken into the factory. The HR madam asked me if I had any work experience or not. And I replied, I have no experience. After that, she called a line chief and the line chief appointed me as a quality inspector as I did not have any required experience. I talked about the salary and the line chief informed me that since I had no skills, they will consider the minimum wage for me. I do not think the procedure follows the compliance rules and regulations. The factory always make discrimination, in terms of

experiences and for the known person.” Participant2: “I got information of the vacancy from one of my relatives, who worked as a supervisor of the factory. I went in front of the gate and called him and he took me inside the factory and placed me in front of a sewing machine and I started my job. The position of my relatives was supervisor there. He looked after the production of a line. He recommended me to the Production manager and the manager allowed me in the factory. I do not agree the factory abides by the compliance rules, regulations in terms of recruitment and I think the wage discrimination can make a poor working conditions for the female migrant workers. Participant3: “I got the hiring declaration of the factory from my neighbor. He got to know about the vacancy, when the HR department declared the vacancy in the factory. Since I had previous experience of the job, I went to the factory gate and I talked to the guards and I was entered into the factory. The supervisor examined me to see if I am fit for the job or not. I passed the examination and the supervisor asked about my experience and as I had one year experience, I got a good amount of salary.” Participant4: “My recruitment experience was flat. I got recruited by a HR employee. She was well known and reputed to the company. She explained about the factory and she prepared the papers for me to complete the formalities. She was from my own village. She took me to the factory and I was examined if I could read and write. I passed and was assigned with a basic salary to the factory.” Participant5: “Getting the job was so significant for me. Since I was poor and my children’s were starving. I took debt from my relative and I left my village. I got the job through my relative. She is an operator of the factory. She talked to the supervisor of the factory and she took me to the factory. I saw the factory for the first time. I entered the factory and my relative took me to the supervisor directly. The supervisor gave me a machine and I started working.” Overall participant sentiment about the hiring procedure was as expected. Either independently or via the efforts of another person, they were hired. The report finds that there was no official process for hiring the staff.

Additionally, based on relationships with employees and past experiences, wage discrimination happens. It was unexpected to see that no one had mentioned the RMG sector's hiring procedures in Bangladesh in the literature. The hiring procedure can make the working conditions for Bangladesh's female migrant employees in the RMG sector worse. According to the report of the research, the hiring procedure leads to discrimination, exploitation, and a lack of rule and regulatory compliance at Bangladeshi RMG factories. The following examples of discrimination, exploitation, lack of compliance rules and regulations and verbal abuse:

4.2 Discrimination of the RMG sector of Bangladesh.

Discrimination has been seen in my study, which has not been mentioned in the literature before. The quote from the participant is as follows: Participant1: “I do think that the factory does adore the employees' relatives, friends, well-wishers and the persons with whom the authorities share a good bond. If any worker is known as a relative of the higher authority, the person gets respect from everyone in the factory. No matter how worse the person's performance is, the person does not get any punishment, which is actually irritating. In terms of wages as well, if you are a relative or a well-known person to the higher authorities or any of the employees, you would get a handsome salary from the factory every month. No matter if you have experience or not. No matter if you can reach production challenges every hour or not, you will get a big amount of salary every month (Sigh). That is how we are getting discriminated and we are deprived.” Participant2: “Discrimination is the main problem of my factory now a days. I do not get enough opportunities like wage, leave, and rest due to the discrimination of the factory. Male, and female workers work in the same working conditions, the recruitment procedure is also the same in my factory for the male and female workers, we are giving the same production every hour though we (female workers) do not get the equal wage like a male worker does. Males are considered superior to the female workers that is why the male workers get more opportunities than the female workers. For example: incentive, appreciation, wage etc. There is another problem with being a woman in the factory. If any woman gets appreciated for her hard work from the authority, supervisor, line chief or anyone of the factory, everyone gets jealous of her and assumes that the woman might have an illegal affair with the person and she is always disrespected. Being a woman is not easy at all”. Participant3: “I think nepotism is the main problem of the RMG sector of Bangladesh. As a worker I was discriminated in my factory since I did not have any work experience. I was discriminated in my factory in terms of wages. As I was new there, I

was perceived as weak, who could give less production. On the contrary, I was giving the same production, as an experienced worker does. Still my salary was minimum and I could not raise my voice against the discrimination, since the salary was important for me to survive". Participant4: "The discrimination is the crucial problem of the RMG sector of Bangladesh. I think the wage, incentive, and appreciation vary according to the familiarity and the face value of the worker. The face value depends on the pretense. The more you can pretend, the more you get face value and as a result your salary gets higher". Participant5: "I got recruited and in front of me I saw the discrimination. I was not that kind of literate and I could barely write. Still I got the highest salary because I am a relative of a higher authority of the factory. At that time I felt good and I continued my job. Gradually, I felt that this is not fair because I saw a lot of qualified and educated people work as a worker like me but they are getting less salary than me. I am not educated though I respect educated people. Only because they were unemployed, they had to continue with the job to survive. It is really heartbreaking".

4.3 Exploitation.

Working conditions for Bangladesh's female migrant workers in the RMG industry. Participant1: "Exploitation raised from the recruitment process of mine. I did not get any appointment letter when I got recruited for the job. I did not get any training as well. Even my recruitment process was not formal enough. Since I did not get any appointment, my job was not secure, which could affect my work place. My leave, rest and vacation was not defined. As a result, I could not seek any assistance from anyone since the environment was new for me. I did not know to whom I should appear for my leave, vacation. Every time I needed to seek guidance from the supervisor and he got annoyed most of the time. I do not get proper rest during the pressure of the production season. There are a lot of pressures during that

season and as a result I could not get enough time to drink water. And forget about going to the washroom. Sometimes, I bore a lot of menstrual pain and could not share it with anybody else in the factory whereas most of the workplaces are male dominated. Even though I went to the medical center, the nurses did not take proper care of me. They forced me to return to the floor and give the production, even though they are women". Participant2: "I have seen a lot of exploitation, in the work journey of the RMG sector. I have seen female workers getting exploited due to lack of skill, education, and lack of identity in the factory. I was exploited as well. Even though I had received minimum education and minimum skills, I was exploited because I was a female worker of the factory. I came from a religious background. I could not get enough time to pray properly. The production team said I pretend to be a religious woman to ignore the production whereas I wanted to pray. There was not enough space in our factory to pray. Since I had to work with a lot of my male colleagues, I had to pray in front of them due to the lack of the prayer hall. Also, during that time, I could not get access to enough health care. I felt hesitate to share my problems with others. Also, I could not maintain purdah properly in the factory". Participant3: "I got recruited independently. I was experienced before and I knew that there is no space for a weak person in the factory. In order to survive you need to speak up and show your potential. I saw a lot of people who could not raise their voice and got exploited. Such as: work pressure. The supervisor will give you more pressure and keep giving until you raise your voice against them. Tell me one thing, if you do not cry to get food, will your mom give you food? I said no. She said, RMG sector is like that. You need to be brave and raise your voice. Otherwise you will get exploited". Participant4: "I was exploited and discriminated due to lack of skills. My salary was the lowest and I did not get my monthly salary on time. The factory used to give me the salary after four or five months. That was not the full amount though. I used to starve day after day. My house owner did not spare me. I need to pay the house rent on time. That is

why I need to sell my gold materials, like rings, chains and pay the rent. My children used to starve and cry for food. During the dull season they fired me from the job and I was jobless. I went to get my earned money since I worked for the factory, but the HR department refused to pay me. I became jobless and I did not know where to go? Only because of being a woman, they could do the exploitation with me (Crying). I am complaining to Allah, He is seeing everything. He will do the justice for me". Participant5: "I was the darling child of my family. Before entering the factory, I was not used to doing a lot of physical work. Since my work hours were not limited, my supervisor forced me to do the overtime, which I did not want to do though. Only because I was not aware of my rights and opportunities could be expected from the factory, I was forced to do excessive work to meet the production. The supervisor was not so kind not only for me, but also for the male and female workers as well. He does not know anything except the production. That is why, his wife eloped. Still he is so cruel. He does not know anything except the work. He works hard and forces us to do excessive hard work which is not tolerable.

4.4 Lack of compliance rules and regulations.

The investigation revealed that the factory employees know very little about the compliances' terms and circumstances. They do not understand their rights. Additionally, they are unaware of what an HR department does at a factory. Some of them think the HR department is a posh factory department. The employers merely walk about and pass their time there, and they are paid at the end of each month. The workforce consider the HR department staff to be useless. The following quotes are from them: Participant1:

"Compliance!!!! It is a fancy issue of our factory. Whenever a buyer comes to do an audit or whenever an auditor comes, then the authorities become busy to ensure that we maintain hundred percent compliance's rules and regulations in our factory. After the buyer or the

auditor leaves, the concept of compliance is forgotten. Compliance seems to me wearing mask, wearing hand gloves etc. to me. I do not think my factory abides by any rules or regulations of compliance. In the recruitment process I do not see my factory to follow any kind of compliance rules or regulations. People come to the factory gate and they get recruited if they have a bonding with the employers or the authorities, is that an application of compliance? Is that the way compliance should be functioned?" Participant2: "In the recruitment process, nobody follows any formal rules and regulations. I did not get any formal declaration of the vacancy. I went to the gate and the guards took me to the factory. I did not face any embarrassing moments during getting recruited. After getting recruited, I got exploited due to lack of implementation of compliance in my factory. Sometimes, I do not get my salary months after months. I do not get enough leave, rest. But I could not raise my voice against it, due to the weakness of the compliance in my factory. They are too weak to arrange a formal recruitment process in the factory, as a result, we do not get any appointment letter from the company. If we raise our voice then there is a fear of either getting fired or the employees will reply, the company is not bound to listen to your complaints. If we say, it is our basic right to get a salary every month, to work eight hours in a day, then they will reply, where has it been written? Can you show any letter where it is written that you will work eight hour only? If you do not want to work, leave the job. We need to stop since we do not get any written form where our rights are written clearly. Also, we do not have money to survive if we leave the job. We are helpless" (Sigh). Participant 4: "I am an acid victim. The horrible face you are seeing right now, that was created by someone else. I used to work hard in the previous factory for my family. My father is a paralysed patient and my mother is a housewife. I have a younger brother. I need to maintain the family by earning money. I was teased by a supervisor every day. He always forced me to love him, but I always refused him. Because I did not like him. I complained against him twice to the HR administration. They

did not look at the condition carefully as he was a local person and also a part of production. The HR department used to say to me, it is quite natural. Try to ignore him. Even though I wanted to change from sewing to finishing, they did not allow me. After days passed, the supervisor got to know that I complained about him. He got furious and while I was returning back to my house from the factory, he threw acid on my face. After that my factory fired me. Is that how the compliance functioned? Is that how the HR department does its duty?"

Participant5: "I do not think compliance is active in my factory. People used to get the job and other opportunities according to their familiarity. Not based on their performance. The procedure is more like buttering. You will get incentive, appreciation, and promotion if you are good enough at flattering the higher authorities. Then you will get enough leave, vacation, rest and salary timely. Otherwise, no matter how much you do for the growth of the factory, you will be ignored. There is no space for any honest person in the RMG factory. You need to abide by dishonesty to survive here.

4.5 Verbal Abuse.

Enveloped into a significant problem. Following are their opinions: Participant1: "My supervisor becomes a devil when I fail to meet the production challenge. I cannot even go to the washroom due to excessive production pressure. My supervisor used to use slang if I do not give production. Sometimes, he uses such slang that cannot be spoken. Same case is applicable for the manager as well. If I pass to give the production, he will not come to me, but unluckily if I fail to do that, he uses slang in front of every workers, employee. Such as: Bustard, mother fucker, daughter of bitch etc. Once upon a time I used to cry in the washroom. I complained about the verbal abuse in the factory, but the attempt was useless. No one cares if you die or alive, you need to meet the production, otherwise supervisor, line chief, manager will use slang and you have to tolerate them. Participant2: "Verbal abuse,

slang are common issues in my factory. The line chief, supervisor, Production manager, manager everyone is pressurized if any line fails to meet the production. For example: the factory manager gives pressure to the production manager. Then the production manager gives pressure to the line chief, and the line chief shows his anger to the supervisor.

Supervisor appears to us and shows all of his anger to us. It is an ongoing problem and it functions chain wise. No one can get rid of this verbal abuse. The abuse is so crucial that no one can ignore this problem. That is why I think I should compromise and try to adopt the environment. Still I am doing so and that is why I am surviving in the atmosphere”.

Participant3: “Verbal use is a common phenomenon in my office. Everyone accepts the problem. Sometimes in front of everyone my boss scolds me as prostitute’s baby and I could not say anything since I had no other options. If I leave the job and shift somewhere else the condition will be the same. All of the Bengali factories used to give pressure to their workers. It is a continuous process that has no end. If anybody wants to raise her voice against it, she will be fired. There is no option to raise voices as the Bengali factories do not allow any trade union. The HR department remains silent if anybody complains about the issue. Moreover, some workers use to do flatteries with the employees and the higher authorities to get promoted. They pass each and every news to the authority and the authority fires the worker who wants to raise her voice. That is why the female workers do not speak up, remain silent and try to tolerate”. Participant4: “I am fired from two of my offices because I spoke against the verbal abuse of the factories. This is my third factory and I have decided not to talk and adopt verbal abuse. Since most of the female workers do not know their basic rights it is foolish to enlighten them and make them aware. That is why, the verbal abuse is raising in my factory, and sexual exploitation is abolished though. My factory is the place where I spend more time than my family. It seems difficult for me to manage my household chores after returning back from the factory. Almost all of the time I need to listen to the slang,

threats of the production despite doing hard work. This is a black fact of the factory and I cannot get rid of the issue”. Participant5: “The verbal abuse is the most common problem in my factory. No matter whether you are a male or female worker, you have to face the consequence of failing the production challenge. Otherwise I have to quit the job and die in starve. This is the reason why I remain silent and try to tolerate. If I feel out of tolerance I cry and after that I try to engage with my work”. But this is a typical occurrence in Bangladesh's Bengali RMG industry. The participants from the EPZ factories claim that the conditions there are better than those in the Bengali factories. They all concurred that they receive their pay on schedule and are not subject to verbal abuse, exploitation, or other distractions. They told me that there is no discrimination at all in their factories and that compliance standards and regulations are upheld.

5. Discussion

The fact that migrant female workers are falling behind in terms of chances and amenities is the reason they are classified as vulnerable. They were meant to have access to all opportunities because they made a greater contribution to Bangladesh's economic success. It is regrettable that they cannot find respectable employment. Although they cannot guarantee a healthy work environment, factories and policymakers should nonetheless have one. Additionally, the start of their adventure is not a formal occasion. They are uncertain as they set off on their journey. I discovered there is discrimination taking place between the factories in the EPZ and the factories in Bengali. I was wondering why there is such a blatant disparity between the factories in the EPZ and the factories in Bengal. The system was the participants' answer. The system, according to a participant in my survey, is the most important component of factory maintenance. The only thing the system looks for is production. With the exception of two of my study's participants, everyone concurred that the attitudes and behaviors vary as a result of rising to the challenge of the performances. If the employee is successful in overcoming the production hurdle, she will continue to perceive the conduct as normal. The overly harsh remarks await them if she is unable to deliver the promised output. That is the most basic description of the RMG industry's working conditions in Bangladesh. The attendees said that there is no formal announcement for employment in the factories. They learn about a factory's vacant position via their loved ones, relatives, neighbors, and well-wishers. Occasionally, some of them are hired independently. They saunter around in front of the factory gates looking for employment. If there is a chance for employment or not, the factory security guards let them know. If there is a vacancy, the security guards accompany them to the factory authority rooms, where they undergo a variety of formal inspections. The most absurd aspect of Bangladesh's RMG sector recruitment process is that, despite failing to provide a minimum formal vacation period for female

migrant workers, the authorities expect female migrants to pass through their purportedly legitimate recruitment process. The female migrants experience salary discrimination after completing their formal procedure since the compliance officers must wait for the line chiefs', supervisors', managers', and controllers' recommendations. The majority of the time, female migrants who have ties to higher authorities are hired. The voiding may have a gory link, be reasonably connected, or be one that the authorities are familiar with. Even when they are the best in their profession, female immigrants may be passed over for jobs while the next applicant is hired regardless of compatibility. The concept of nepotism is nowadays applicable for the recruitment process of the RMG sector in Bangladesh. The reason for this compatibility is that female immigrants now receive training in areas such as running machinery, meeting manufacturing techniques, and fabric sewing. Additionally, they are conversant with a few machine mechanisms used in the RMG industry. As a result, they are no longer considered to be performing unskilled labor. If they demand a minimum pay in line with their excellence, it is only natural. Surprisingly, the recruiters in Bangladesh's sector do not recognize their abilities; rather, they are seen as unskilled female laborers. The fact that the labor was crucial for their survival prevented the female migrants from speaking out against the discrimination. They are being halted in the very beginning of their working lives in this manner. When they are being recruited, they do not receive appointment letters. Because of this, they are not aware of their rights at work, and their employment is still unstable. Additionally, salary discrimination is based on gender identification. Because girls are viewed as weaker as and less productive than male workers, they occasionally do not receive the same pay as men. In contrast, both male and female employees devote time to the same workplaces and carry out the same tasks. The participants contend that because the hiring procedure does not adhere to compliance guidelines, it has an impact on their working conditions. They sometimes have to wait months to receive their pay since it is not delivered

on schedule. They do not get enough sleep and only leave when necessary. Due to the high production demands, they are forced to work in an unsanitary environment and lack the time to use the restroom or drink water. Moreover, ladies are reluctant to discuss their menstrual issues with the supervisors because they are largely male. Despite the fact that they visit the health center, the nurses continue to be irresponsible and send them back to the floor. They do not get enough rest and only go when it's really necessary. They are compelled to work in an unhygienic setting because of the high production needs, and they do not have enough time to use the restroom or drink water. Additionally, because supervisors are predominantly male, women are hesitant to disclose their menstruation problems with them. The nurses continue to be careless and send them back to the floor despite the fact that they go to the health center. Also, they do not spend much time relaxing once they get home. They must care for the family, feed the members, and prepare for further conflict tomorrow. As a result, the female workers are at risk for dehydration, cancer, skin conditions, and numerous other serious illnesses. They still fight because they want to be financially secure; sometimes their goals come true, and other times they pass away before they can. Despite having a huge number of negative aspects, a matter of hope is the study found that the sexual exploitation or the assault are not addressing in the RMG sector of Bangladesh any more. The factories pose strictly against the sexual assault and harassment. In addition, nobody is allowed to touch a worker intentionally. No matter what the designation of an employee carries, he is not allowed to apply his body parts to harass the workers. The terms and conditions are applicable to both female and male workers of the factories. As a result, the sexual harassment has been demolished from the RMG sector which was observed before. The most absurd aspect of the material currently in circulation is that while most authors highlighted the significance of female migrant workers to Bangladesh's RMG sector, they also noted its issues and subpar working conditions. In addition, the authors also talked about the

connection between Bangladesh's RMG industry and its female migrants. They demonstrated how, because female workers in Bangladesh's RMG sector are falling behind, their sorrows and suffering are being disregarded while women are being exploited in the name of empowerment. However, nobody brought up the Bangladeshi RMG sector's hiring practices. This study's special problem is that. Because they are tied to one another, I wanted to draw attention to the RMG sector's hiring practices and the subpar working conditions it provides for female migrant workers in Bangladesh. Given that they make up a larger share of the sector, female migrant workers are essential to any discussion of Bangladesh's RMG industry. They make a significant contribution to the economy's cycle of activity. It is terrible that some authors claim that their issues are not being taken seriously. On the other hand, other writers asserted that every literary work already adequately highlights female migrants. That is a completely unrelated subject. Nobody examines how female migrants manage to get employment in Bangladesh's RMG sector after shifting to urban areas. Because it marks the beginning of migrant female workers' lives, the recruitment process for the RMG sector is crucial to examine. For a migrant female worker, the recruitment procedure also produces an unsanitary workplace that may last until she quits her job. Because the foundation of a factory is represented by the hiring procedure. The workers can anticipate a minimal level of formality and acceptable attitudes from the factory if it begins in a formal setting. However, if it begins in an informal environment, the employees will not anticipate a formal outcome from the factory. Additionally, the hiring process includes the functioning of female employees and an explanation of their rights in addition to serving as a worker's initial point of contact. As an illustration, during the hiring process, a worker is informed of the wage that will be determined for her labor. Since a worker's income is one of their fundamental rights, the manufacturer determines how much they will pay each employee each month by setting their compensation. Since the factory addresses fundamental rights throughout the hiring

process, it might be argued that it is educating people about their rights at work. If the recruitment procedure does not inform her of her rights, she loses consciousness in this realm. She experiences discrimination and verbal abuse as a result, and in the end, she attempts to either accept the situation or quits her employment. In terms of familiarity, face value, and charming skills, women workers are subject to discrimination, according to the second finding of this study. The majority of participants concurred that because they are unfamiliar with the hierarchy, they are discriminated against and undervalued. They include the fact that they do not receive the required recognition from their factories and that they earn less money than workers with lower levels of expertise because they are unable to appease the authorities. The disparity between male and female workers was underlined in literature, but no one talked about the disparity between female and female workers. The participants added that if their factories are not occupied by any employees or higher authorities, they do not receive the respect they deserve from them. Which could be addressed from the recruitment process of the sector. Additionally, segregation was also strongly evident in the EPZ and Bengali factories. Compared to the employees of the factories in Bengal, those in the EPZ factories have more opportunities. For instance, Bengali manufacturing workers occasionally do not receive their paychecks on time, whereas EPZ workers always receive their pay on time. The employees of Bengali factories do not have access to opportunities like this, while the EPZ employees receive two hours of extra time, rest, and proper leave. As a result, the employees of the factories in Bengal lag behind in terms of accessing opportunities. Numerous scholars have claimed that there may be discrimination between workers in a factory. They did not specify that the factories might offer a variety of options. Some factories offer their employees greater amenities, while others do not. Additionally, it is a problem that might be important to look at. The factory workers also hold the entire political establishment responsible for their woes and pains. They contend that the failure of the

government or policymakers to guarantee the rights of the factory employees who fuel the economic cycle is their fault. The paradoxical thing is that we have a tendency to refer to them as being weak, even though, if we gave it some serious thought, we should be appreciative of their contribution to the foreign exchange market. This essay aims to investigate the RMG industry's subpar working conditions and recruitment tactics in Bangladesh. I must design the questions such that participants' responses can address the issues that can be brought to light in order to study the actual conditions. I have therefore made an effort to discuss the hiring procedure, the working environment, the pay, and the exploitation aspect. The participants answered my questions and responses without holding back. Surprisingly, they want to do away with the exploitation and discrimination I highlighted earlier. The majority of workers believe that this nation's political system is corrupt. I concur with their assertion because the policy brief, which could be emphasized throughout the entire nation, will encompass ensuring someone's rights and protecting the essential component of workers' rights. The workers in Bangladesh's RMG sector do not speak out about their suffering because they do not participate. As a result, they continue to contribute to economic progress and growth while receiving nothing in return. Because the rights-based approach is discussed in a portion of the development studies, I have addressed development here. A rights-based strategy argues for more equitable resource distribution and support for marginalized groups in claiming their rights to such resources. Thus, it clearly politicizes the development process (Cornwall et al., 2004). To ensure the workers' rights and accommodate a decent work sphere in the RMG sector of Bangladesh, the policy makers or the government should focus on the people who are existing at the bottom. A bottom-up approach analyses the "multitude of actors who interact at the operational (local) level on a particular problem or issue" and focuses on the "strategies pursued by various actors in pursuit of their objectives" (Sabatier, 1986, p. 22, as cited in Carolus et al., 2018). Such

problems or issues therefore serve as the starting point of a bottom-up approach, and thus determine the relevant actors. Being commonly accepted as one component in environmental planning (Human & Davies, 2010; Koontz & Newig, 2014, as cited in Carolus et al., 2018), the benefits of including local stakeholders in policy planning processes go beyond its democratic value and the possibilities (Carolus,2018). I am discussing the bottom-up method and the rights-based approach in this article since Bangladeshi RMG workers are thought of as the country's downtrodden population who are denied opportunities and healthy lifestyles. Expect them since without them, which are more prevalent in our country, development is impossible. We must take care of the underserved and marginalized population if we want to guarantee a developed country. Development is nothing more than an unsatisfied aspiration without them. There are connections between the RMG industry, female migrants, RMG workers, rights-based approach, bottom-up approach, and development. It is impossible to maintain harmony without one of them. They are significant to note and were not previously mentioned in the literature.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study reveals that Bangladesh's RMG industry has made a significant contribution to the country's economic growth. Female migrant workers from rural and urban areas make up a larger share of the workforce. Despite helping Bangladesh's economy thrive, the workers there have unclean lives because to lax enforcement of laws and regulations in their workplaces, verbal abuse, exploitation, and discrimination. Which genuinely carried out from the sector's hiring process. Because the process has the appearance of a factory, I am emphasizing the hiring methods of Bangladesh's RMG industry. If a factory accepts official recruitment procedures there, it was reasonable to assume that the plant would provide a comfortable working environment for its employees. It is regrettable

that the factories are unable to provide their employees with a structured working atmosphere. Since there is no official disciplinary action taken against the employees throughout the hiring process, they take the circumstances for granted and endeavor to fit in with the informal atmosphere, which includes decency, modesty, and honor.

6.1 Future Directives for the RMG sector of Bangladesh.

Due to the government, policy makers, and factory owners' lack of care, discrimination and verbal abuse occur in Bangladesh's RMG industry, as this study has demonstrated. Since female migrant workers in Bangladesh's RMG sector are an important part of the country as well, the government and policy makers should apply the bottom-up and rights-based approaches more. The factory owners should treat all employees fairly so that workers' concerns are brought to light. The concepts vary from person to person because owners and morals, ethics, philosophy, and psychology are all subjective. That could be the cause of your discrimination in the factories. Even if the factories are under a lot of production pressure, the owners can disguise themselves to observe how the operations are run and think about any variables that may affect the female migrant employees. They could consider the issues of the unhygienic working conditions and they should try to solve them. The HR department should be stricter to implement the compliance rules and regulations in the factories so that the exploitation can be reduced. As the factories are dependent on the workers' production, it is the owners responsibility to look after if the workers are well facilitated or not in their factories.

6.2 Limitations of the Study.

The data cannot be generalized because it was gathered from a few EPZ firms and three Bengali factories in Bangladesh's RMG industry. The study's primary gap is this. If they so choose, the researcher could include more factories. Although they weren't covered in depth, the study brought attention to the hiring practices and working conditions in Bangladesh's RMG industry and showed how they connect to development. In the future, the researcher may concentrate more intently on the intricate connections between the RMG sector and development so that the contribution of the female migrant workers gets acknowledged more. The difficulties facing female RMG workers could be brought to light more as their contributions are recognized. People would develop a stronger bond with the female migrant workers as a result of reading the stories, and they would also take action to improve the situation. Additionally, research involves taking action as well as gathering facts and organizing it beautifully in a paper. The more issues are brought to light, the more they may be resolved.

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Appendices

Appendix A:

Questionnaires on Recruitment Process of RMG sector in Bangladesh

Below is a list of the questions that will be used to perform the research:

Name of the participant (Optional):

Age:

Contact number:

Location:

Section A: Recruitment process

1. How did you first get the information about the job in your factory? Who gave you that information?

2. How were you recruited in your factory? Can you explain the process please in detail?

3. Did you find anyone who was playing the most crucial role in your recruitment process??

Explain in detail. (Yes or no)

4. If your answer is yes, could you please mention his position and role in your factory?

Explain in detail.

5. How did that person help you get recruited? Explain in detail.

6. Do you think there will be some other factors who are working behind the recruitment process? If so, who are they?

7. Please explain your overall experience at the time of recruitment. 8. Did you find any devastating embarrassing conditions at the time of recruitment for being recruited?

-If yes, could you please explain the scenario? Did you report your experience to anybody?

-If yes, do you think that many women workers face similar experiences?

9. Could you please explain if you have seen any women workers experiencing embarrassing situations at the time of recruitment? What kind of situation was that? 10. What are the positions that could be eradicated in terms of recruitment processes?

12. Do you think some other factors are getting benefited during the recruitment process?

-If so, could you please specify who they are?

13. Do you think the recruitment process ensures the compliance's rules and regulations?

-If so, could you please explain the rules and regulations that you are talking about? If not, can you please explain what is lacking in the recruitment processes of the RMG sector in Bangladesh?

Section B: Types of recruitment processes

1. Which kind of recruitment process was applied to you while you were recruited? (Explain)

2. Do you think there might be some other recruitment processes which exist in the other RMG industries of Bangladesh? If so, what are they?

3. Could you please explain the processes of recruitment in the RMG sector of Bangladesh?

4. How many recruitment processes are you familiar with?

5. Could you please explain which process is more devastating embarrassing for migrant female workers of the RMG sector in Bangladesh? (Explain why?)

6. Did your recruitment process affect you mentally? (Explain how?) Section C: Poor working conditions

1. Do you feel that the existing recruitment processes are creating discrimination in terms of wages in the industries?

-If so, please explain the details of created discrimination.

2. How did you feel while you were seeing yourself discriminated against?

3. Did your recruitment process affect you mentally? (Explain how?)

4. Do you think the recruitment processes create some unethical and hazardous Work conditions? (If so, explain how?)

5. What distinctions exist between male and female employees in your factory? Do they have the same working conditions?

6. What are the risks of working as a woman worker?

7. How many hours do you work? Do you get overtime, leave and rest? 8. Does your employer pay your salary regularly?

9. Do you face any difficulty in maintaining work-life balance?

10. Did you experience any verbal or sexual assault at work?

11. Did you see anybody experience any verbal or sexual assault at work?

12. Are you able to negotiate your wage and other benefits with your employer?

13. How does your manager behave with you? Please explain in detail.

14. Are you a member of a trade union?

-If yes, why?

-If no, why not?